

WAYS TO IMPROVE DEMAND FORMATION AND SALES PROMOTION AT OR GOLDEN OIL LLC

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Abstract. This article examines the policy of demand formation and sales promotion, compliance with the life stages of the product in the market, and the ability to attract customers to the product.

Keywords: enterprise, market, commodity, demand, supply, competition, consumer, need, quality, strategy.

ПУТИ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СПРОСА И СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ СБЫТА В ООО «ОР ГОЛДЕН ОЙЛ»

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается политика формирования спроса и стимулирования сбыта, соблюдение жизненных стадий товара на рынке, возможность привлечения клиентов к товару.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, рынок, товар, спрос, предложение, конкуренция, потребитель, потребность, качество, стратегия.

INTRODUCTION

Along with improving the quality and competitiveness of the products produced by OR GOLDEN OIL LLC, it is important for the buyer to have the ability to pay for the sale of the goods. Therefore, the demand is also called "solvent demand".

When buying goods, people intend to satisfy certain needs. Therefore, it is a responsible period for the company to enter the market, information about the quality indicators of the goods is not provided. The prospective consumer must receive the following information:

- availability of goods and place of sale;
- which needs are aimed at satisfaction;
- basic indicators of consumer value;
- guarantees to protect customers in the event of dissatisfaction.

Methods of communicating information to prospective buyers:

- Advertisements (radio, television, written).
- Conducting exhibitions.
- Meetings through conferences and films.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Addressing uninformed buyers will stimulate their demand and encourage them to buy the product.

So, one of the main reasons for the formation of demand is to be able to interest customers in the product by providing them with correct and accurate information about the product, and attracting the consumer with the appearance and packaging of the product.

Sales promotion refers to consumers who have a certain level of information about the product. Therefore, the task of the incentive policy is to make them eager to buy the company's goods in the future and to encourage them to keep in touch.

Demand generation activities are usually aimed at consumers and sellers. Incentives for consumers are intended to provide them with significant commercial benefits:

- a privilege given to the volume of purchase of goods and to stay in constant contact;
- sale of goods for various forms of debt;
- distribution of samples free of charge with a view to purchasing goods in large quantities;
- free supply of goods for temporary use;
- acceptance of used goods under certain conditions;
- showing new goods to prospective buyers;
- organization of trips to enterprises producing goods;
- conducting press conferences dedicated to the introduction of new products to the market;
- announcements on the radio, television and press about a sharp reduction in the price of goods.

The promotion policy for the products depends on the type of customers who buy them. It is intended to encourage intermediaries, to increase their activity and initiative, and to expand the circle of consumers. The policy of demand formation and sales promotion must correspond to the life stages of the product in the market and give appropriate content to each of them.

It is used by most buyers who do not have information about the product or are not affected by its high price. Attracting buyers, forming their demand is organized by spending a lot of money on events. It is assumed that the price of the goods will be set high and that a lot of profit will be made.

Selective market entry method.

It is used when its size is not large. The product is unknown to many people, even if it is given a high price, customers can buy it. There are very few competitors in the market and therefore it is possible to make more profit with less cost to stimulate demand.

A method of extensive market penetration. This method is used when the market size is large, buyers have little impression of the product and do not agree with its price. In addition, the competition is strong, as a result of increasing the production of goods, their cost will decrease and there will be conditions for "increasing prices". It will be possible to allocate more funds to incentives.

With a slow marketing style, when the size of the market is large, customers know the product well, success is achieved through lower costs, lower prices, and less competition.

The growth stage of the product market begins to squeeze competitors due to the fact that consumers are more familiar with the product that has entered the market. If the market is big, competitors will also start producing goods similar to ours. New types of products and new customers are developed for the market against competitors. During this period, various events are held to update the model of some goods and to form a demand.

In advertising, the characteristics of the product tested in the practical experience of consumers are highlighted more, benefits and price reduction are used.

In the product market period, at this stage, the full assortment of goods is included in the market, and more than 50% of buyers are provided with the desired goods. Now the goods are mainly bought by buyers with a conservative outlook. Demand promotion activities are mainly focused on highlighting the usefulness of the product.

Saturation of the commodity market. During this period, the goods are mainly sold at the expense of consumers' repurchases in the market. The policy of stimulating demand will be ineffective. Therefore, goods with good demand are left on the market. But advertising is not weakened, but rather strengthened. The price is reduced and the product is brought closer to the majority of buyers.

A period of depression in the commodity market. At this stage, demand and sales promotion activities are suspended for this product. Incentive measures aimed at sellers are mainly carried out in order to increase the volume of sales of goods: monetary rewards, additional days off, valuable gifts, moral incentives, advertising of enterprise activities, etc.

The specifics of marketing problems at "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC first of all require improvement of the marketing strategy planning process. These improvement paths will depend on the changes in the market and corresponding changes in the types of strategies.

RESULTS

The latest research on market trends shows that the following new trends are emerging in the juice and alcoholic beverage market:

- Increased focus on consumption changes in the oil market. Nowadays, among oil products of the same quality, well-known and fashionable ones are chosen by consumers, as they focus more on utility aspects. Another important aspect of this is that fashion sometimes creates situations that do not respond to logic. In addition, the frequent changes in fashion have a great impact on the state of the juice market.

- Consumers pay more attention to product safety. The modern consumer pays more attention to its beneficial properties than to the oil itself, and when choosing it, he certainly thinks about his health. For this reason, the purity and naturalness of oil-oil products is important.

- Increasing consumer expectations. An increase in the standard of living leads to a greater demand for the product. The requirements for vegetable oils are getting stronger every year. Especially from new types of oils, buyers expect real freshness, which increases the responsibility of manufacturers. I think the lack of success of safflower and soybean oils in the domestic market is the inability to meet the growing demand.

- The improvement of technologies leads to the emergence of many new processes and equipment in the field of oil production. Although the term of the equipment at "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC does not exceed 5 years, it is appropriate to pay attention to their renewal, because now new equipment is created every year.

- Globalization, that is, the disappearance of borders between markets, is another important factor in the change of the market environment. The opening of opportunities to enter the foreign market has a great influence on the choice of strategy.

Changes in the market environment can include requirements for the scope and quality of services, changes in attitudes toward brands, increased competition, changes in the relationship of goods to individual categories, and others.

These changes lead to new conclusions and understanding of new strategies in the analysis and evaluation of the market environment.

As a result of changes in the consumer market, "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC requires the use of marketing strategies in addition to the above strategies:

- a) Speed marketing, i.e. product creation, presentation, market capture and drastically reducing the following strategy is very important to apply to sunflower oil.

Such a strategy, along with increasing its position in the market, will make it possible to create very popular brands for future buyers. In addition, the specified strategies can be tried on some wholesale bases.

b) Adjustment of oil products to specific (personal) needs of consumers. Such a strategy can be applied to non-traditional products of society. Abroad, this experience has been used for many years, that is, each type of vegetable oil has its own properties and is being passed on to consumers. This is the basis for the segmentation of the oil products market.

c) Quality assurance strategy. This strategy occupies a very small place among marketing strategies. According to scientists, the existing strategy is close to management. But based on the demand of the time, it is justified that the quality of products and services is related to marketing in juice production. Therefore, the product quality strategy can be taken into account when choosing a marketing strategy.

g) struggle, dominance and cooperative strategy. This strategy comes from the existence of different consumers in the market. Full satisfaction of their requirements cannot be achieved by a single organization, so it is necessary to choose a strategy that recognizes the interconnectedness of all similar organizations in the competitive struggle. "Competition-advantage-cooperation" strategy is to fight within a single solution, to achieve the development of professional superiority and to cooperate together with all manufacturers to meet the needs of the common market.

DISCUSSION

Based on the above characteristics, we propose to use new approaches in the development of a strategy for the "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC production partnership society.

For example: In order to expand the traditional market, it is appropriate to implement a strategy to improve sales by pouring juice to customers. For this purpose, it is desirable to offer an additional product that improves the quality of the oil. At the same time, consideration of the issues of improving the activity of juice markets will have a great effect.

Improving the strategy production process requires the implementation of certain measures by the leadership of the society. Such measures include the creation of strategic business units. In the theory of marketing strategy, strategic business units are defined as units that deal independently with a particular segment or product. It is desirable to create such independent groups in "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC. For example: a strategic business unit for safflower oil. Or a strategic business unit for olive oil. Independent strategic business units develop and implement strategies for market success of these oils. A strategic business unit includes a representative of the management, the official heads of the relevant department, a representative of the marketing department and other persons selected by the working group. The strategic business unit acts as an advisory committee to management, continuously developing recommendations and plans for safflower oil market expansion. The activity of the strategic business unit is evaluated and rewarded not by individual tasks, but by the final result - the amount of market capture. Then the scheme of the strategic marketing process will also change.

The use of this procedure allows for a separate approach for each type of product and, in our opinion, leads to an increase in market position.

According to the results of the end-of-year reports, the economic condition of the enterprise is good, but the financial independence of the organization should be increased, it is necessary to reduce the difficulties of financial risk in the future, and it is necessary to guarantee that the enterprise fulfills its obligations at a high level.

CONCLUSIONS

The company was able to cover its liabilities through private equity. Currently, the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC is selling its products to all regions of the Republic, selling products through wholesale and direct agreements with customers, wholesale databases and customers.

In order to expand the assortment of oil products and improve product quality, it is appropriate to develop new types of oil production technologies by the organization's specialists.

In the strategy implemented by the Republic of Uzbekistan for the development of the market economy mechanism, the role of science is incomparable, which will certainly be the main impetus for the change of the investment program. In this regard, we believe that the organization of marketing service at the production enterprise of "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, creating the necessary conditions for its full activity is one of the most urgent tasks before the enterprise.

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